

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/vertnet
hash://md5/9d608263b2c4b4d2f30a36634b758796

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/vertnet, has fingerprint hash://md5/9d608263b2c4b4d2f30a36634b758796, is 2.60GiB in size and contains 196,782 interactions with 12 unique types of associations (e.g., parasiteOf) between 16,984 primary taxa (e.g., Arthropoda) and 29,025 associated taxa (e.g., Acari). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Abilene Christian University Insect Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.34 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=acunhc_ento 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Abilene Christian University Marine invertebrate Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.34 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=acunhc_inv 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Alabama Museum of Natural History Insect Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.38 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=almnh_ento 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Alabama Museum of Natural History Invertebrate Zoology (Arctos) - Version 1.39 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=almnh_inv 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Alabama Museum of Natural History Paleontology specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.44 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=almnh_paleo 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Angelo State Natural History Collections (ASNHC) Amphibian and reptile specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.71 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=asnhc_herp 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Angelo State Natural History Collections (ASNHC) Bird specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.69 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=asnhc_bird 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Angelo State Natural History Collections (ASNHC) Mammal specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.67 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=asnhc_mamm

2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Austin Peay State University Amphibian and Reptile Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.34 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=apsu_herp
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Austin Peay State University Fish Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.34 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=apsu_fish
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Brigham Young University (BYU) Herpetology Collection (Arctos) - Version 3.29 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=byu_herps
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Brigham Young University Life Science Museum (BYU) Mammal Collection (Arctos) - Version 1.59 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=byu_mamm 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z California State University, Long Beach Bird specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.39 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=csulb_bird
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z California State University, Long Beach Mammal specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.42 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=csulb_mammals
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z CHAS Botany Collection (Arctos) - Version 13.104 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=chas_herb
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z CHAS Entomology Collection (Arctos) - Version 13.104 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=chas_ento
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z CHAS Malacology Collection (Arctos) - Version 13.105 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=chas_inv 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z CHAS Mammalogy Collection (Arctos) - Version 13.101 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=chas_mammals
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z CHAS Oology Collection (Arctos) - Version 14.103 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=chas_eggsnest
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z CHAS Ornithology (Arctos) - Version 2.101 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=chas_birds 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z DMNS Bird Collection (Arctos) - Version 34.103 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=dmns_bird 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z DMNS Egg Collection (Arctos) - Version 19.105 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=dmns_egg 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z DMNS Herp Collection (Arctos) - Version 1.60 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=dmns_herp 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z DMNS Mammal Collection (Arctos) - Version 34.103 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=dmns_mamm 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z DMNS Marine Invertebrate Collection (Arctos) - Version 20.98 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=dmns_inv 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z DMNS Parasite Collection (Arctos) - Version 34.100 <https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=dmn> 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Harold W. Manter Laboratory of Parasitology Collection (HWML) Parasite Collection (Arctos) - Version 1.60 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=hwml_para 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Kenai National Wildlife Refuge, Alaska (KNWR) Fish observations (Arctos) - Version 1.73 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=knwrobs_fish 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Kenai National Wildlife Refuge, Alaska (KNWR) Insect specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.72 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=knwr_ento 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Kenai National Wildlife Refuge,

Alaska (KNWR) Invertebrate specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.70 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=knwr_inv 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Kenai National Wildlife Refuge, Alaska (KNWR) Plant specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.71 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=knwr_herb 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Kenneth S. Norris Center for Natural History, University of California, Santa Cruz (UCSC) Amphibian and reptile specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.71 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=ucsc_herp 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Kenneth S. Norris Center for Natural History, University of California, Santa Cruz (UCSC) Bird specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.72 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=ucsc_bird 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Kenneth S. Norris Center for Natural History, University of California, Santa Cruz (UCSC) Mammal specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.72 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=ucsc_mamm 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z KWP Lepidoptera Collection (Arctos) - Version 1.102 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=kwp_lepidoptera 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z MLZ Bird Collection (Arctos) - Version 33.106 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=mlz_bird 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z MLZ Mammal Collection (Arctos) - Version 33.106 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=mlz_mamm 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z MSB Amphibian and Reptile Collection (Arctos) - Version 1.99 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=msb_herp 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z MSB Bird Collection (Arctos) - Version 35.103 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=msb_bird 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z MSB Fish Collection (Arctos) - Version 1.86 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=msb_fish 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z MSB Host Collection (Arctos) - Version 34.103 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=msb_host 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z MSB Mammal Collection (Arctos) - Version 35.106 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=msb_mamm 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z MSB Parasite Collection (Arctos) - Version 32.103 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=msb_para 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Museum of Vertebrate Zoology Fish Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.30 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=mvz_fish 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z MVZ Bird Collection (Arctos) - Version 43.101 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=mvz_bird 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z MVZ Bird Observations (Arctos) - Version 34.110 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=mvzobs_bird 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z MVZ Egg and Nest Collection (Arctos) - Version 37.105 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=mvz_egg 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z MVZ Herp Collection (Arctos) - Version 36.100 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=mvz_herp 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z MVZ Herp Observations (Arctos) - Version 37.105 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=mvzobs_herp 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z MVZ Mammal Collection (Arctos) - Version 35.102 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=mvz_mammal 2026-

06-02T22:00:39.245Z New Mexico Museum of Natural History and Science (NMMNH&S) Herbarium specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.64 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=nmmnh_herb 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z New Mexico Museum of Natural History and Science (NMMNH&S) Insect specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.65 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=nmmnh_ento 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z New Mexico Museum of Natural History and Science (NMMNH&S) Invertebrate specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.64 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=nmmnh_inv 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z New Mexico Museum of Natural History and Science (NMMNH&S) Mammal specimens (Arctos) - Version 9.61 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=nmmnh_mammals 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z New Mexico Museum of Natural History and Science (NMMNH&S) Paleontology specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.67 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=nmmnh_paleo 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Northern Michigan University (NMU) Bird specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.97 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=nmu_bird 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Northern Michigan University (NMU) Mammal Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.100 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=nmu_mamm 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Northern Michigan University (NMU) Parasite specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.25 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=nmu_para 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Ohio Wesleyan University Amphibian Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.42 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=owu_amph 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Ohio Wesleyan University Bird Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.51 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=owu_bird 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Ohio Wesleyan University Fish Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.51 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=owu_fish 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Ohio Wesleyan University Invertebrate Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.51 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=owu_inv 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Ohio Wesleyan University Parasite Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.55 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=owu_para 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Ohio Wesleyan University Reptile Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.50 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=owu_rept 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z TEST_MSB Mammal Collection (Arctos)_TEST - Version 35.107 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=test_ggbn_msbmamm_test 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Trinity College Dublin Geological Museum Paleontology specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.31 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=tcdgm_paleo 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UAM Bird Collection (Arctos) - Version 31.102 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uam_bird 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UAM Earth Sciences Collection (Arctos) - Version 31.107 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uam_es 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UAM Fish Collection (Arctos) - Version 34.104 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uam_fish 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UAM Herbarium (ALA), Algae Collection (Arctos) - Version 8.105 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uam_alg

2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UAM Herbarium (ALA), Cryptogam Collection (Arctos) - Version 33.104 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uamb_herb_cryptogam
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UAM Herbarium (ALA), Vascular Plant Collection (Arctos) - Version 38.104 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uam_herb_vascular
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UAM Herpetology Collection (Arctos) - Version 31.105 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uam_herp
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UAM Insect Collection (Arctos) - Version 39.105 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uam_ento
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UAM Insect Observations (Arctos) - Version 36.103 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uamobs_ento
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UAM Invertebrate Collection (Arctos) - Version 31.96 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uam_inv
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UAM Mammal Collection (Arctos) - Version 34.101 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uam_mamm
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UAM Mammal Observations (Arctos) - Version 31.105 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uamobs_mamm
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UCM Amphibian and Reptile Collection (Arctos) - Version 17.106 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=ucm_herps
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UCM Bird Collection (Arctos) - Version 16.106 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=ucm_birds
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UCM Bird Eggs/Nests Collection (Arctos) - Version 16.107 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=ucm_egg
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UCM Fish Collection (Arctos) - Version 18.110 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=ucm_fish
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UCM Mammal Collection (Arctos) - Version 17.107 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=ucm_mammals
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UCM Parasite Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.15 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=ucm_para
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UCM Vertebrate Observations Collection (Arctos) - Version 16.105 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=ucm_obs
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UMNH Mammals Collection (Arctos) - Version 2.92 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=umnh_mammals
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UMNH Reptiles and Amphibians Collection (Arctos) - Version 2.94 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=umnh_herps
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z University of Alaska Anchorage Insect Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.29 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uaa_ento
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z University of Montana Zoological Museum (UMZM) Bird Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.33 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=umzm_bird
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z University of Montana Zoological Museum (UMZM) Mammal Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.31 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=umzm_mamm
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z University of Nevada, Reno (UNR) Amphibian and Reptile Specimens (Arctos) - Version 10.30 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=unr_herps
 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z University of Nevada, Reno (UNR) Bird specimens (Arctos) - Ver-

sion 1.29 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=unr_bird 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z University of Nevada, Reno (UNR) Mammal Specimens (Arctos) - Version 4.28 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=unr_mammals 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z University of North Carolina Greensboro Mammal Collection (Arctos) - Version 1.45 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uncg_mamm 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z University of North Carolina Greensboro Parasite Collection (Arctos) - Version 1.9 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uncg_para 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z University of Wisconsin Zoological Museum Amphibian and Reptile Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.9 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uwzm_herp 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z University of Wisconsin Zoological Museum Bird Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.8 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uwzm_bird 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z University of Wisconsin Zoological Museum Mammal Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.9 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uwzm_mamm 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z University of Wyoming Museum of Vertebrates (UWYMV) Bird Collection (Arctos) - Version 30.108 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uwymv_bird 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z University of Wyoming Museum of Vertebrates (UWYMV) Mammal Collection (Arctos) - Version 31.105 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uwymv_mamm 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UNM Earth Sciences Collection (Arctos) - Version 1.101 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=unm_es 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UTEP Birds (Arctos) - Version 1.101 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=utep_bird 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UTEP Fossils (Arctos) - Version 1.101 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=utep_es 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UTEP Herpetology (Arctos) - Version 1.84 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=utep_herp 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UTEP Herpetology Osteology (Arctos) - Version 10.75 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=utep_herp_oste 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UTEP Insects (Arctos) - Version 1.101 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=utep_ento 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UTEP Invertebrates (Arctos) - Version 1.102 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=utep_inv 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UTEP Mammals (Arctos) - Version 10.108 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=utep_mamm 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UTEP Plants (Arctos) - Version 5.113 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=utep_herb 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UWBM Herpetology Collection (Arctos) - Version 31.106 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uwbm_herp 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z UWBM Mammalogy Collection (Arctos) - Version 4.100 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=uwbm_mammals 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z Washington State University, Charles R. Conner Museum Bird Specimens (Arctos) - Version 1.25 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=ccrm_bird 2026-06-02T22:00:39.245Z WNMU Bird Collection (Arctos) - Version 31.104 https://ipt.vertnet.org/archive.do?r=wnmu_bird

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11
nomer	0.6.5
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 2.60GiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/vertnet

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/vertnet \
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/vertnet \
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/vertnet \
```

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/vertnet`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/vertnet`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/vertnet`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/vertnet`)

```
| nomer append col \  
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

You can find a copy of the full review script at `check-data.sh`. See also GitHub and Codeberg.

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in Appendix A. Review Files.

Archived Dataset

Note that `data.zip` file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/vertnet, has fingerprint hash://md5/9d608263b2c4b4d2f30a36634b758796, is 2.60GiB in size and contains 196,782 interactions with 12 unique types of associations (e.g., parasiteOf) between 16,984 primary taxa (e.g., Arthropoda) and 29,025 associated taxa (e.g., Acari).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped csv, tsv, geopackage and parquet archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped html page at indexed-interactions.html.gz are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Arthropoda	parasiteOf	Clethrionomys rutilus	https://arctos.database.museum/guid/UAM:Ent
Arthropoda	parasiteOf	Peromyscus keeni	https://arctos.database.museum/guid/UAM:Ent
Arthropoda	parasiteOf	Microtus abbreviatus	https://arctos.database.museum/guid/UAM:Ent
Arthropoda	parasiteOf	Sorex tundrensis	https://arctos.database.museum/guid/UAM:Ent

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
parasiteOf	70347
interactsWith	47169
adjacentTo	30375
hasParasite	27085
coOccursWith	11764
killedBy	6281
hasHost	3109
eats	327
eatenBy	133
visitsFlowersOf	96
hostOf	91
visits	5

interactionTypeName	count
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Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Arthropoda	8384
Acari	7675
Siphonaptera	6607
Peromyscus maniculatus	3773
Cestoda	3491
Nematoda	2865
Dipodomys merriami	2770
Peromyscus leucopus	2639
Phthiraptera	2338
Taenia	1869
Ixodida	1831
Toxascaris	1748
Myodes gapperi	1625
Echinococcus multilocularis	1532
Polyplax borealis	1485
Myodes rutilus	1328
Bombus melanopygus	1268
Dipodomys ordii	1075
Ochotona princeps	1019

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Acari	5473
Alopex lagopus	4328
Siphonaptera	4307
Clethrionomys rutilus	3312
Microtus oeconomus	2801
Dipodomys merriami	2734
Peromyscus maniculatus	2537
euthanasia	2295
window	1990
Peromyscus keeni	1727
Sorex cinereus	1695

targetTaxonName	count
Ixodida	1619
Myodes rutilus	1548
Phthiraptera	1441
Microtus pennsylvanicus	1366
vehicle	1235
Aythya affinis	1204
Ochotona princeps	1121
Nematoda	1071

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Arthropoda	parasiteOf	Clethrionomys rutilus	1625
Taenia	parasiteOf	Alopex lagopus	1303
Arthropoda	parasiteOf	Peromyscus keeni	1083
Toxascaris	parasiteOf	Alopex lagopus	1049
Siphonaptera	parasiteOf	Peromyscus maniculatus	993
Peromyscus maniculatus	hasParasite	Siphonaptera	850
Arthropoda	parasiteOf	Microtus oeconomus	814
Arthropoda	parasiteOf	Sorex cinereus	578
Echinococcus multilocularis	parasiteOf	Alopex lagopus	574
Echinococcus multilocularis	parasiteOf	Microtus oeconomus	514
Polyplax borealis	parasiteOf	Clethrionomys rutilus	514
Echinococcus	parasiteOf	Alopex lagopus	471
Mastophorus dipodomis	parasiteOf	Dipodomys merriami	441
Dipodomys merriami	hasParasite	Mastophorus dipodomis	441
Arthropoda	parasiteOf	Sorex monticolus	438
Eimeria chobotari	parasiteOf	Dipodomys merriami	429
Dipodomys merriami	hasParasite	Eimeria chobotari	429
Uncinaria	parasiteOf	Alopex lagopus	415
Arthropoda	parasiteOf	Microtus pennsylvanicus	398

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

You can download the indexed dataset under review at indexed-interactions.csv.gz. A tab-separated file can be found at indexed-interactions.tsv.gz

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration `indexed-interactions.map` :

```
MAP
  SIZE 1600 800
  EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
  PROJECTION
    "init=epsg:4326"
  END
  LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
    NAME "modis_nasa"
    TYPE RASTER
    OFFSITE 0 0 0
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
    CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"

  METADATA
    "wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
    "wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
    "wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
    "wms_format" "image/jpeg"
  END
  CLASS
    STYLE
      COLOR 232 232 232
      OUTLINECOLOR 32 32 32
    END
  END
  LAYER
    NAME "indexed-interactions"
    TYPE POLYGON
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
    CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
    DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
    CLASS
      STYLE
```

```

        COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
        DATARANGE 0.3010299956639812 4.350945431337479
        RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
        OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
    END
END
END
END
END

```


Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at `indexed-interactions.gpkg` for point data and `indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg` for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Slope	NONE	col	Slope
Rock	NONE	col	Rock
Diameter rock edge	NONE	col	Diameter rock edge
Diameter mossy rock	NONE	col	Diameter mossy rock

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	14015
col	class	27
col	family	283
col	form	2
col	genus	1714
col	infraorder	4
col	kingdom	3
col	order	44
col	parvorder	2
col	phylum	10
col	species	13727
col	subclass	3
col	subfamily	19
col	subgenus	44
col	suborder	7
col	subphylum	4
col	subspecies	1060
col	subterclass	1
col	superfamily	11
col	superorder	3
col	tribe	26
col	variety	113
discoverlife	NA	30719
discoverlife	species	100
gbif	NA	13971
gbif	class	26
gbif	family	286
gbif	form	22
gbif	genus	1733

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
gbif	kingdom	3
gbif	order	37
gbif	phylum	11
gbif	species	13684
gbif	subspecies	1150
gbif	variety	270
itis	NA	18331
itis	class	23
itis	division	2
itis	family	259
itis	genus	1275
itis	kingdom	3
itis	order	46
itis	phylum	11
itis	species	9793
itis	subclass	12
itis	subdivision	1
itis	subfamily	13
itis	subgenus	2
itis	suborder	12
itis	subphylum	4
itis	subspecies	856
itis	superfamily	10
itis	superorder	4
itis	tribe	3
itis	variety	181
mdd	NA	30818
ncbi	NA	17647
ncbi	clade	4
ncbi	class	25
ncbi	cohort	1
ncbi	family	272
ncbi	genus	1541
ncbi	infraorder	3
ncbi	kingdom	2
ncbi	order	42
ncbi	phylum	11
ncbi	species	10852
ncbi	subclass	10
ncbi	subfamily	21
ncbi	subgenus	29
ncbi	suborder	9
ncbi	subphylum	4
ncbi	subspecies	324

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
ncbi	superfamily	18
ncbi	superorder	4
ncbi	tribe	4
ncbi	varietas	28
pbdb	NA	28010
pbdb	class	25
pbdb	family	210
pbdb	genus	721
pbdb	informal	1
pbdb	infraclass	1
pbdb	infraorder	3
pbdb	kingdom	3
pbdb	order	44
pbdb	phylum	13
pbdb	species	1725
pbdb	subclass	5
pbdb	subfamily	23
pbdb	suborder	11
pbdb	subphylum	1
pbdb	subspecies	15
pbdb	subtribe	1
pbdb	superclass	1
pbdb	superfamily	11
pbdb	superorder	3
pbdb	superphylum	1
pbdb	tribe	5
pbdb	unranked clade	13
tpt	NA	29123
tpt	family	19
tpt	genus	121
tpt	order	5
tpt	species	1551
wfo	NA	23923
wfo	family	21
wfo	genus	632
wfo	phylum	1
wfo	species	6084
wfo	subsection	1
wfo	subspecies	142
wfo	variety	78
worms	NA	24348
worms	class	24
worms	family	238
worms	genus	910

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
worms	infraorder	1
worms	kingdom	3
worms	order	43
worms	phylum	9
worms	phylum (division)	1
worms	species	4992
worms	subclass	8
worms	subfamily	5
worms	subgenus	1
worms	suborder	10
worms	subphylum	3
worms	subphylum (subdivision)	1
worms	subspecies	213
worms	subterclass	1
worms	superclass	1
worms	superfamily	14
worms	superorder	2
worms	variety	30

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	22693
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	22166
col	SYNONYM_OF	8359
discoverlife	NONE	50575
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	168
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	41
discoverlife	HOMONYM_OF	14
gbif	NONE	22691
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	24730
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	9343
itis	NONE	27626
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	17628
itis	SYNONYM_OF	2902
mdd	NONE	45810

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1758
mdd	SYNONYM_OF	21
ncbi	NONE	29992
ncbi	SAME_AS	19165
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	1769
ncbi	COMMON_NAME_OF	17
pbdb	NONE	41524
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	5868
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	479
tpt	NONE	43204
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	4473
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	200
wfo	NONE	37612
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	2517
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	8360
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	735
worms	NONE	37861
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	9343
worms	SYNONYM_OF	1185

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

catalog name	alignment results
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-03T12:06:15Z	note	found unresolved reference [0010041JSNM]
2026-06-03T12:06:15Z	note	found unresolved reference [0010043JSNM]
2026-06-03T12:06:15Z	note	found unresolved reference [008f0ec3-68fd-4051-b53e-13b594a29545]
2026-06-03T12:06:15Z	note	found unresolved reference [00b8b626-b09e-4bc8-a2d2-7235f7382605]

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 12: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
found unresolved reference [0010041JSNM]	1
found unresolved reference [0010043JSNM]	1
found unresolved reference [008f0ec3-68fd-4051-b53e-13b594a29545]	1
found unresolved reference [00b8b626-b09e-4bc8-a2d2-7235f7382605]	1

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-03) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: “Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.”

filename	description
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map

filename	description
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads

filename	description
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

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